

'Visual Evoked Potential': A Tool for Assessing Underlying Deficit in Low Academic Achievers

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ABSTRACT

Poor academic performance among students requires due attention. It might be a symptom reflecting an underlying physiological problem. Any problem in the visual processing of the information could be one of the contributory factors of the poor academic performance. Visual evoked potential (VEP) is a sensitive & reliable parameter to assess the functional integrity in visual pathway. Present study has investigated the relationship of poor academic performance among students with visual processing of the information. The academic scores of final examinations of preceding 2 years were assessed among 18-25 year aged college youth. These were divided under two categories namely 'high academic achievers' (>80% in 10th & 12th Board) and 'low academic achievers' (<50% in 10th & 12th Board) with 40 participants in each group. VEP was recorded by LED Goggles method in 'Octopus Clarity Machine'. In low achievers, latency of N75 and P100 were significantly prolonged. The latency of N135 showed no difference among both the groups, but the amplitude of VEP (P100-N135) was found to be significantly reduced in low achievers as compared to high achievers. Weaker VEP response in low achievers could be due to some defect in central neural processing of the visual information. Thus, VEP can be used as a tool to assess the underlying deficit in low academic achievers.

KEY WORDS: academic performance, high achievers, low achievers, P100 amplitude, P100 latency, VEP

INTRODUCTION:

Academic performance of an individual is influenced by many factors like physiological variables (genetic composition), holistic environment (family, society & school) during growth & development, psychological factors and socio-economic status of the individual. All the psychosocial factors influence the physiological outputs like neurophysiologic outputs, personality traits and academic performance. Hence poor academic performance might be a symptom reflecting an underlying physiological problem in many of the students, thereby requiring due attention.^[1] There are basically 3 stages of information processing – input (information processed by auditory or visual senses), integration (interpreted, categorized placed in sequence or related to previous learning) and output

(language output or muscle activity)^[2].

Any problem in the visual processing of the information could be one of the contributory factors of the poor academic performance. Visual evoked potential (VEP) is used for assessing the integrity and functioning of visual pathway from retina to visual cortex. The VEP is obtained from the optic tract by recording the evoked potentials generated by retinal stimulation^[1]. It is one of the sensitive & reliable parameter to assess the neural processing of time in visual pathway. There are small number of reported studies related to the relationship of neuro-physiological outputs and academic performance. Farah khaliq et al^[1] studied VEP in slow learners (school going children) and found significant prolongation of N75 latency. The present study was aimed to investigate the relationship between poor academic performance and visual processing of the information.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The present study was conducted in the Neurophysiology Laboratory, Department of Physiology, People's Medical College and Research

Center, Bhopal. The subjects were selected from amongst the students of various constituent institutes of People's University. 400 students of aged 18-25 years were screened for their academic performance in 10th & 12th standard.

The students with scores above 80% in 10th & 12th board exams and with teachers and parents' report of attentiveness, interest and learning behavior were categorized under 'high academic achievers', while students with scores below 50% in 10th & 12th board exams with teachers and parents report of inattentiveness, disinterest or hyperactive behavior were categorized under 'low academic achievers'. A total of 80 subjects, 40 high achievers and 40 low achievers from similar socio-economic background, were clinically evaluated for refractory errors and neurological testing was done. The students with uncorrectable refractory errors and with any neurological problems were excluded from the study. Psychiatric consultation was done for all subjects to rule out any psychiatric problem. Those who were mentally fit were selected for the study. The students with any major psychological or physical trauma (demise of parents, financial loss, personal illness etc) affecting the studies were excluded from the study. The height and weight measurements were taken for all subjects to calculate BMI to match the nutritional status of subjects (Table 1). Written consent was taken from all the subjects of the study. The study was commenced after obtaining clearance from the institutional research advisory committee.

RECORDING OF VEP:

The selected subjects were called in the Department of Physiology in batches of 10, one day prior to their VEP recording and were familiarized with the procedure. The subjects were instructed to report to the Neurophysiology Laboratory of Physiology Department with adequate rested night sleep, washed hairs with no oils or sprays. They were instructed to avoid use of any type of eye drops. They were asked to bring glasses or contact lenses, if they wear those. The subject was seated comfortably in a quite darkened room. The visual ERPs P100 was recorded by the 'Octopus Clarity-EMG/EP/NCS' machine.

The recording electrode was placed at Oz, the reference electrode at FPz and grounding electrode at Cz using conducting jelly as per 10-20 international system of EEG electrode placement after cleaning the

scalp^[3]. The skin electrode contact impedance was kept less than 5 K . The calibration of the manufacturers was accepted as accurate. Visual stimulator provided with flash Light Emitting Diode (LED) Goggle was used to stimulate the retina and VEP recording was done. The flash subtended at least 20 degree and had stimulus strength of 1.5-3cd/m² (as per manufacture of the machine).

Total of 300 responses were recorded and averaged by the computer of the evoked potential recorder with low and high frequency filters 1-200 Hz. Typical NPN pattern was recorded in both the groups. The absolute latency and amplitude of waves of VEP were observed and analyzed.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

The data obtained was analyzed using SPSS software (Version 20.0). Results were expressed as Mean±SD. Unpaired 't' test was used to compare between the low achievers and high achievers.

RESULTS:

VEP was recorded in 40 high academic achievers and 40 low academic achievers. Both the groups were matched in Age & BMI (table1). VEP waveform in both the groups showed typical NPN pattern (as shown in Graphical records: first N is abbreviated for N75, P is abbreviated for P100 and second N is abbreviated for N135).

We found significant prolongation of latency of N75 and P100 in low achievers (Table 3 & 4). The latency of N135 showed no difference among both the groups. But the amplitude of P100-N135 was found to be significantly reduced in low academic achievers (Table 5) as compared to high achievers.

DISCUSSION:

VEP results are a representation of the functional integrity of the visual pathway including the retina, optic nerve, optic chiasma, lateral geniculate nucleus and visual cortex. Any abnormality that affects the visual pathways or visual cortex in the brain can affect VEP^[5]. Latency measurements can reveal issues affecting vision if it takes more time for the electrical signals to reach the visual cortex.^[4]

P100 Latency (Peak Time), measured in milliseconds (ms), indicates the time the electrical signal takes to travel from the retina to the visual cortex. The P100 of VEP is generated in the striate & peri-striate occipital cortex not only due to activation

Table 1: Age & BMI of both the Groups.

	High Achievers (n=40)	Low Achievers (n=40)	p value
Age (Years)	19.37±1.94	19.87±2.13	>0.05
BMI	20.3±1.45	19.84±0.89	>0.05

Table 2 : Average scores of last 2 years in Percentage.

Groups	Mean	p value
High academic Achievers(n=40)	92 ± 5.7834	< 0.05
Low Academic Achievers(n=40)	48 ± 1.4830	

Table 3: Latency of VEP (P100 wave) among High & Low Academic Achievers.

Groups	Mean	't' test value	p value
High academic Achievers (n=40)	100.27 ± 1.72	-34.463	<0.05
Low Academic Achievers (n=40)	123.60 ± 3.22276		

Table 4: Latency of N75 among High & Low Academic Achievers.

Groups	Mean	't' test value	p value
High academic Achievers (n=40)	65.4 ± 1.48	-13.463	<0.05
Low Academic Achievers (n=40)	76.8 ± 2.56		

of primary occipital cortex but also due to thalamocortical volleys (Mishra & Kalitha^[3]). The exact generator sources and temporal sequences of these are not well defined. Research with multichannel scalp recordings, visual MRI activity and dipole modeling, supports the interpretation that

the visual cortex is the source of early component of VEP (N1, N70) prior to P1 (P100). The early phase of P1 component with a peak around 95-110msec, is likely to be generated in dorsal extrastriate cortex of the middle occipital gyrus. The later negative component N2 is generated from several areas including a deep source in the parietal lobe^[5]. There was observed significant prolongation of latencies of N75 & P100 in low achievers as compared to high achievers in the present study, while the late component showed no delay in processing. Our results are indicative of some delay in early phase of visual processing in low achievers.

Table 5: Amplitude of P100 (P100-N135) among High & Low Academic Achievers

Groups	Mean	't' test value	p value
High academic Achievers (n=40)	9.17 ± 2.36	27.09	<0.05
Low Academic Achievers (n=40)	3.28 ± 1.11		

Graph 1: Graphical record of VEP of high achiever..

Graph 2: Graphical Record of VEP of Low Achiever.

Latency measurements tend to have less variation than amplitude both within-subject and between subjects. The combination of amplitude and latency is helpful in determining the functional integrity of the visual pathway. Low amplitude of P100 wave (Table 4) in low academic achievers was observed in the present study. Amplitude of P100 wave, measured in microvolts (μV), indicates the amount of electrical energy reaching the visual cortex. Amplitude is calculated as the absolute difference between P100 and N-135 microvolt measurements (shown in Graphical record)^[4]. Generally, amplitudes are a measure of “how much” information is reaching the visual cortex. For example, the number of retinal cells being stimulated will affect the amplitude. Amplitude will also vary with the vision system's ability to process a particular sized stimulus. An increase in amplitude typically relates to better ability of discrimination for different sized objects. In general, as the patient has more difficulty seeing the stimulus, it will evoke a smaller electrical response, thus creating smaller amplitudes^[4]. Low amplitude found in low achievers in our study is

suggestive of problem in perceiving the information.

There are no other related studies that have studied relationship of VEP with academic performance except Farah khaliq¹ et al (2009) study, who studied VEP in slow learners (school going children) and found significant prolonged latencies of N75. The significant prolongation of N75 in our study is matching with the above study. The prolongation of P100 latency in their study could not reach the level of significance. The sample size of slow learners was only 17 which could be the reason for not getting the statistically significant findings of P100 in their study. We found significant prolongation of P100 latency in our study which could be due to relatively larger sample size ($n=40$) in our study. In addition to the latencies of VEP, the amplitude of P100-N135 is also found to be significantly reduced in low achievers in our study which has not been considered and mentioned in their study. VEPs quantify visual system function. Abnormal VEPs can be symptomatic of dysfunction, but are not diagnostic of it until carefully considered with the context of patient's clinical picture^[5]. We can conclude that prolonged latencies of N75 and P100 observed in our study might be suggestive of a delay in the processing of neural information via visual pathway in low academic achievers and reduced amplitude is suggestive of less amount of information reaching the brain. The subjects with weaker VEP response should be further evaluated for exact location of the problem in the visual pathway.

Unless structural and functional integrity are assessed, low academic achievers should not be held responsible for their low performance. Further extensive studies with larger sample size are needed for in-depth understanding of the related physiological processes.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

Gender variation of VEP was not considered in our study.

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